

Automatic Abstraction Refinement for Hyperproperties Verification (Extended Version of IJCAR’26 Paper)

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Abstract. This paper proposes a novel automatic abstraction-refinement procedure for verifying hyperproperties. Hyperproperties specify the behavior of a system across multiple executions, and are an important extension of standard temporal properties. Our verification procedure is based on predicate abstraction and the recently introduced reduction of hyperproperty verification to satisfiability of Constrained Horn Clauses (CHCs). Moreover, it formalizes and uses CHC-based refinement for abstract counterexamples in the shape of directed acyclic graphs. We implemented our new algorithm on top of the SMT solver Z3. Our experimental evaluation shows our automatic abstraction refinement procedure can solve a variety of hyperproperty verification problems, completely automatically. This is in contrast to other existing techniques that require a user-given abstraction.

1 Introduction

Verification of hyperproperties [11] is notorious for being computationally hard. Hyperproperties encode relations between multiple traces of a program (or programs), and extend standard temporal logic by allowing quantification (universal and existential) over traces. As a result, verifying hyperproperties requires a few ingredients that depend on one another: (i) finding *relational* inductive invariants; (ii) finding an *alignment* that determines how different traces are executed; and (iii) finding witness traces in case the hyperproperty includes existential trace quantifiers. The dependency between the different ingredients is what makes hyperproperty verification complex [30,33,6,23].

A well known approach for handling the complexity of verification is *abstraction-refinement* [10,21,26]. Abstraction provides a mechanism for removing parts of the concrete program and creating a smaller *abstract program* [17,4], by that reducing the complexity of verification. However, abstraction comes at the cost of precision and the abstract program may include spurious counterexamples even if the concrete program satisfies the property. In case a spurious counterexample is found, a *refinement* procedure is invoked. The goal of refinement is to eliminate that spurious counterexample, and create a refined, more precise abstract program. This process is iterated until either the property is proved, or a real counterexample is found.

In this paper we present a novel *automatic* abstraction-refinement algorithm for the verification of hyperproperties, based on a new formalization of abstraction-refinement in the context of non-linear Constrained Horn Clauses (CHCs) [7]. Our algorithm, **AbsHyHorn**, builds on our recently introduced reduction of hyperproperty verification to satisfiability of CHCs [23]. The reduction presented in [23] delegates the search for all three aforementioned hyperproperty verification ingredients to a CHC solver (instead of fixing some of them apriori). While this greatly improves the performance of hyperproperty verification, the resulting CHCs are *non-linear*, therefore posing a challenge even for state-of-the-art CHC solvers [25,22,8]. For that reason [23] relies on user-provided abstraction predicates, from which the solution to the CHCs is constructed. Notably, since all necessary ingredients reason about multiple traces, the predicates needed are often *relational*. In contrast to [23], **AbsHyHorn** automatically synthesizes the relevant predicates, requiring no input from the user.

As noted, **AbsHyHorn** uses *predicate abstraction* [17,4,16,9]. Given a set of predicates \mathbb{P} , it encodes the hyperproperty verification problem as a set of CHCs $\Pi_{\mathbb{P}}$, which is an abstraction of the concrete encoding Π . Both Π and $\Pi_{\mathbb{P}}$ consist of non-linear CHCs. If $\Pi_{\mathbb{P}}$ is satisfiable, then so is the concrete encoding Π , which means that the hyperproperty is verified. Otherwise, $\Pi_{\mathbb{P}}$ is unsatisfiable and an abstract counterexample is found. While counterexamples to linear CHCs (as in safety verification), have the form of a single trace, in the case of $\Pi_{\mathbb{P}}$, non-linearity of the CHCs entails that the proof of unsatisfiability and the counterexample it represents have the shape of a *directed acyclic graph* (DAG). For example, if the property is a k -safety hyperproperty, which states that a tuple of k traces never reaches a “bad configuration”, then the counterexample “contains” k traces that violate the property for *every* possible interleaving of the k traces.

Upon detecting an abstract counterexample, **AbsHyHorn** invokes a refinement procedure that is likewise based on a CHC encoding. Using the DAG-shaped proof of unsatisfiability, a new set of *refinement* CHCs, Π_R , is created. Π_R is defined in terms of the *concrete* states, and can be understood as an unrolling of Π according to the counterexample. Importantly, unlike the original set of CHCs Π , which is recursive, Π_R is not recursive, and therefore easier to solve. If Π_R is unsatisfiable then a real counterexample is found, which means that the hyperproperty does not hold. Otherwise, if Π_R is satisfiable, then the counterexample is spurious. In this case, **AbsHyHorn** extracts new predicates from the solution of Π_R , adding them to \mathbb{P} . Although this method resembles refinement techniques based on tree/DAG interpolants [19,27,29,1,3], it avoids the need to explicitly expand the DAG into a tree or a sequence, and thus sidesteps the complexity introduced by such an expansion.

Lastly, once **AbsHyHorn** synthesizes the required predicates, it performs a *generalization* step with the goal of learning “better” predicates for refinement. Our generalization heuristic is tailored towards hyperproperty verification since it focuses on generating relational predicates.

We implemented **AbsHyHorn** on top of Z3 [28], using Spacer [25] as a CHC solver and evaluated it on a set of benchmarks that includes hyper-safety (k -

Fig. 1: Two programs and the CHC encoding of a 2-safety property.

safety) and hyper-liveness properties ($\forall^* \exists^*$ -OHyperLTL properties [6]). While previous approaches require user-provided predicates in order to solve these benchmarks, and the latest CHC-based tool from [23] cannot solve most of them when using the concrete programs, **AbsHyHorn** can solve all properties (but one) completely automatically, without any user-provided predicates.

To summarize, our contributions are as follows: (i) a novel *automatic* abstraction-refinement algorithm for verification of $\forall^* \exists^*$ -OHyperLTL hyperproperties; (ii) a formalization of CHC-based refinement for DAG counterexamples; and (iii) a predicate generalization heuristic for generating relational predicates.

1.1 Motivating Example

Consider the two programs F_1 and F_2 in Figure 1. A valid 2-safety property for these two programs states that at the beginning of the i -th iteration of the outer loop, the value of x in F_1 (x^1) equals the value of x in F_2 (x^2). This 2-safety property follows from the fact that $x^1 = x^2$ holds at the beginning of the inner loop, provided we consider only even iterations of F_1 's inner loop. Such a proof requires a non-standard alignment.

When reducing this 2-safety problem to satisfiability of CHCs [23] using the concrete semantics (i.e. without abstraction), **Z3** cannot solve it given a two hours timeout. We use this example throughout the paper to demonstrate a few of the key elements of our approach.

2 Preliminaries

Throughout this paper, we use the standard syntax and semantics of first-order logic (FOL). Since we only consider satisfiability modulo theories, we fix a background first-order theory \mathcal{T} and denote its signature by Σ . We denote the set of Σ -formulas over a set of variables X as $\mathcal{F}(\Sigma, X)$, and the set of Σ -terms as

$T_\Sigma(X)$. Given a Σ -formula η , we denote by $Vars(\eta)$ and $Atoms(\eta)$ the set of free variables and the set of atoms that appear in η , respectively. Lastly, given a substitution $\sigma : Vars(\eta) \rightarrow T_\Sigma(\emptyset)$ that maps variables to *closed terms*, we denote by $\eta[\sigma]$ the result of substituting every free variable v in η with $\sigma(v)$.

2.1 Constrained Horn Clauses

Let P^U be a set of fresh predicate symbols, called *uninterpreted predicates*, s.t. $\Sigma \cap P^U = \emptyset$. Constrained Horn Clauses (CHCs) are closed formulas over the signature $\Sigma \cup P^U$ of the form: $\forall X \cdot (\bigwedge_{i=1}^n P_i(X_i) \wedge \eta(X) \rightarrow H(X_H))$ where X is a set of variables; $\eta(X)$ is a quantifier-free Σ -formula with free variables X , and $P_i(X_i)$ is an application of an uninterpreted predicate $P_i \in P^U$ with $X_i \subseteq X$; The part $(\bigwedge_i P_i(X_i) \wedge \eta(X))$ is called the *body* of the CHC; $H(X_H)$ is called the *head* and is either \perp or an application of an uninterpreted predicate from P^U with $X_H \subseteq X$. The universal quantification over X is often omitted for brevity. We say a CHC is linear if its body contains at most one application of a predicate from P^U . Otherwise, it is called non-linear. Moreover, a CHC is *normalized* if $X_H \cap (\bigcup_{i=1}^n X_i) = \emptyset$. In the sequel we only consider normalized CHCs.

CHC Satisfiability modulo \mathcal{T} . Given a finite set of CHCs Π , the problem of deciding if Π is satisfiable (modulo \mathcal{T}) is called CHC-SAT. The set Π is satisfiable if it has a satisfying model M such that the projection of M onto Σ is a model of \mathcal{T} . CHC solvers, however, do not search for arbitrary satisfying models, and instead look for a *solution* in the form of a Σ -interpretation. A Σ -interpretation \mathcal{I} for Π is a map that assigns to every uninterpreted predicate $P \in P^U$ a Σ -formula $\mathcal{I}(P)$ over variables Y_P . For $\pi \in \Pi$, we denote by $\mathcal{I}(\pi)$ the Σ -formula obtained through substitution of every uninterpreted predicate application $P_i(X_i)$ in π with its interpretation $\mathcal{I}(P_i)[Y_{P_i} \leftarrow X_i]$. A Σ -interpretation \mathcal{I} is a *solution* of Π , denoted $\mathcal{I} \models_{\mathcal{T}} \Pi$, if $\mathcal{I}(\pi)$ is \mathcal{T} -valid for every $\pi \in \Pi$. If a set of CHCs has a solution then it is satisfiable (SAT). However, the converse may not hold due to the limited expressive power of first-order formulas.

A set of CHCs Π is unsatisfiable (UNSAT) iff \perp is derivable from it using the following *Hyper-Resolution* inference rule:

$$\frac{\forall X \cdot \eta(X) \wedge P_1(X_1) \wedge \dots \wedge P_n(X_n) \implies H(X_H), \quad P_1(X_1)[\sigma], \dots, P_n(X_n)[\sigma]}{H(X_H)[\sigma]}$$

where:

- $\forall X \cdot \eta(X) \wedge P_1(X_1) \wedge \dots \wedge P_n(X_n) \implies H(X_H)$ is a CHC $\pi \in \Pi$.
- $\sigma : X \rightarrow T_\Sigma(\emptyset)$ is a substitution such that $\models_{\mathcal{T}} \eta(X)[\sigma]$.

We denote this inference rule as HYPERRES and use HYPERRES(π, σ) to indicate an application of the rule on a CHC $\pi \in \Pi$. We refer to $P_1(X_1)[\sigma], \dots, P_n(X_n)[\sigma]$ as the *ground* premises of the rule.

If Π is UNSAT, the derivation of \perp is represented by a *directed acyclic graph* (DAG), to which we refer as a *hyper-resolution proof* of unsatisfiability of Π .

Throughout this section, given a DAG $G = (V, E)$ and a node $v \in V$, we denote by $in(v) = \{u \in V \mid (u, v) \in E\}$ the set of nodes on its incoming edges.

Definition 1. Let Π be an unsatisfiable set of CHCs, where X is a set of variables used in Π . A hyper-resolution proof of unsatisfiability for Π is a finite directed acyclic graph (DAG) $G_\Pi = (V, E, r, L_S, L_F)$ where:

- $V = V_T \uplus V_I$ is a set of nodes, where V_T are terminal nodes with no incoming edges, and V_I is a set of internal nodes.
- $E \subseteq V \times V$ is a set of directed edges, such that $\forall v \in V_I \cdot |in(v) \cap V_T| = 1$; The unique terminal node leading to v is denoted by $in_T(v)$.
- $r \in V_I$ is the root (no outgoing edges).
- $L_S : V_I \rightarrow T_\Sigma(\emptyset)^X$ is a labeling function mapping V_I to substitutions.
- $L_F : V \rightarrow \mathcal{F}(\Sigma, X)$ is a labeling function mapping V to FOL formulas s.t.: (1) $L_F(r) = \perp$; (2) $\forall v \in V_T : L_F(v) \in \Pi$; and (3) $\forall v \in V_I : L_F(v)$ is the consequence of $\text{HYPERRES}(L_F(in_T(v)), L_S(v))$ where $\{L_F(v') \mid v' \in in(v) \cap V_I\}$ are the ground premises of the rule.

2.2 Hyperproperty Verification

Transition Systems. A transition system is a tuple $TS = (\mathcal{V}, Init, Tr)$, where \mathcal{V} is a vector of variables denoting state variables; $Init$ is a formula over Σ with free variables in \mathcal{V} representing the initial states, and Tr is a formula over Σ with free variables in $\mathcal{V} \cup \mathcal{V}'$, representing the transition relation (\mathcal{V}' consists of the primed variants of \mathcal{V}). A state of TS is a valuation to \mathcal{V} . A trace of TS is an infinite sequence of states $t = s_0, s_1, \dots$ such that for every $i \geq 0$ $(s_i, s_{i+1}) \models Tr$, where (s_i, s_{i+1}) should be understood as a valuation to $(\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{V}')$. For $i \in \mathbb{N}$, we define $TS^i = (\mathcal{V}^i, Init^i, Tr^i)$ as a copy of TS , where variables in \mathcal{V} are substituted by $\mathcal{V}^i := \{v^i \mid v \in \mathcal{V}\}$.

Hyperproperties. We consider formulas in the $\forall^* \exists^*$ fragment of OHyperLTL [6]:

$$\varphi \triangleq \psi \rightarrow \forall \pi_1 : \xi_1, \dots, \pi_\ell : \xi_\ell. \exists \pi_{\ell+1} : \xi_{\ell+1}, \dots, \pi_k : \xi_k. G \phi,$$

where π_i are trace variables over the set of traces \mathbb{T} , ξ_i are Σ -formulas over \mathcal{V}^i that define the observation points where traces synchronize, ψ is the precondition on the initial states of the k traces, and ϕ is the safety formula required to hold globally at all synchronization points. Both ψ and ϕ are Σ -formulas over $X := \mathcal{V}^1 \cup \dots \cup \mathcal{V}^k$. When $\ell = k$, φ expresses a k -safety property; otherwise, it generalizes to $\forall^* \exists^*$ hyperproperties that capture relational liveness aspects.

$\forall^* \exists^*$ -OHyperLTL formulas are interpreted over transition systems: φ holds in a transition system if from every k initial states that jointly satisfy the precondition ψ , and for every ℓ traces from the first ℓ states, there exist corresponding $k - \ell$ traces from the remaining $k - \ell$ states such that the composed states of all traces globally satisfy ϕ , when projected to their observation points.

Hyperproperty Verification as CHCs. Verifying hyperproperties is challenging since it requires the discovery of relational inductive invariants, which relate states of k execution traces. As a result, verification of such properties requires finding an *alignment* of any k traces, where the alignment determines how the different traces advance in tandem. In the case of hyperliveness properties (in the $\forall^*\exists^*$ -OHyperLTL fragment), verification also requires witness traces (due to existential quantifiers) that match the universally quantified traces and the alignment.

In [23], we show how verification of $\forall^*\exists^*$ -OHyperLTL properties can be reduced to CHC-SAT, which allows the witness traces, alignment of traces and relational inductive invariants to be constructed simultaneously. For simplicity of presentation, we present the key ideas for the universal fragment of $\forall^*\exists^*$ -OHyperLTL (namely, k -safety properties). The interested reader is referred to [23] for the complete presentation.

Let $TS = (\mathcal{V}, \text{Init}, \text{Tr})$ be a transition system and φ a k -safety property. Deciding if $TS \models \varphi$ requires either finding a counterexample, which is a set of k traces that shows why φ does not hold, or finding an *alignment* and a *relational inductive invariant* that proves φ holds in TS . For the latter, it is natural to consider a composed transition system $\hat{TS} := TS^1 \times \dots \times TS^k$. We refer to a state in \hat{TS} as a composed state. A composed state is a valuation over $\mathcal{V}^1 \times \dots \times \mathcal{V}^k$.

The CHC-SAT reduction in [23] captures the alignment by introducing an arbiter that, given the current composed state, selects a non-empty subset of traces $\emptyset \neq M \subseteq \{1, \dots, k\}$ to advance. We refer to such M as a *schedule* and the set of all possible schedules is denoted as $\mathbb{M}_k = \mathcal{P}(\{1, \dots, k\}) \setminus \{\emptyset\}$. In addition to being non-empty, a schedule M must also be *valid*: only traces that are not already at a synchronization point can advance in the current step, or if all traces are at a synchronization point – all advance together. We encode validity of a schedule M using the predicate $\text{valid}_M(X)$ (see [23] for details).

Following the notion of an arbiter and schedules, in order to encode the problem into CHCs, in [23] we define uninterpreted predicates that represent *doomed states*. A composed state \hat{s} is *doomed* if for every schedule (alignment), \hat{s} eventually reaches a bad state that violates the property φ . This results in the following set of CHCs:

Definition 2. Let $TS = (\mathcal{V}, \text{Init}, \text{Tr})$ be a transition system and let φ be a k -safety hyperproperty with precondition ψ . Let $\{D_M \mid M \in \mathbb{M}_k\}$ be a set of uninterpreted predicates. We define the set of CHCs $\Pi(TS, \varphi) := \{\text{fact}_M, \text{rule}_M, \text{query} \mid M \in \mathbb{M}_k\}$ where

$$\begin{aligned} \text{fact}_M &:= (\text{Bad}(X') \vee \neg \text{valid}_M(X')) \wedge X' = X \rightarrow D_M(X) \\ \text{rule}_M &:= \bigwedge_{M'} D_{M'}(X') \wedge \delta_M(X, X') \rightarrow D_M(X) \\ \text{query} &:= \bigwedge_M D_M(X) \wedge \bigwedge_i \text{Init}(\mathcal{V}^i) \wedge \psi(X) \rightarrow \perp \end{aligned}$$

where $X = \bigcup_{i=1}^k \mathcal{V}^i$, $\text{Bad}(X) = \bigwedge_i \xi_i(\mathcal{V}^i) \wedge \neg\phi(X)$ and $\delta_M(X, X') = \bigwedge_{i \in M} \text{Tr}^i(\mathcal{V}^i, \mathcal{V}^{i'}) \wedge \bigwedge_{i \notin M} (\mathcal{V}^i = \mathcal{V}^{i'})$ encodes transitions according to schedule M .

For simplicity of presentation, the above definition considers k copies of the same transition system. Therefore, each Tr^i is the result of substituting \mathcal{V} and \mathcal{V}' in Tr with \mathcal{V}^i and $\mathcal{V}^{i'}$, respectively. Note that the CHCs are normalized.

We use X' and X in fact_M to ensure it is normalized. This is only done for simplicity of presentation in the following section. The *doomed* CHCs encoding presented above provides a sound and complete characterization of k -safety:

Theorem 1 ([23]). *Let $TS = (\mathcal{V}, \text{Init}, \text{Tr})$ be a transition system and let φ be a k -safety hyperproperty. $TS \models \varphi$ iff $\Pi(TS, \varphi)$ is satisfiable.*

Example 1. The CHCs encoding for the motivating example (Section 1.1) appears in Figure 1. Note that $\mathcal{V}^i = \{x^i, y^i\}$ is the set of variables and Tr^i is the transition system for F_i , where $i \in \{1, 2\}$. The schedule is represented by M : if $M = \{1\}$ only F_1 executes, if $M = \{2\}$ only F_2 executes, and if $M = \{1, 2\}$ both F_1 and F_2 execute.

3 Automatic Predicate Abstraction Refinement for CHCs

We now describe an automatic abstraction refinement procedure for verification of $\forall^*\exists^*\text{-OHyperLTL}$. Throughout this section we fix a transition system TS , a $\forall^*\exists^*\text{-OHyperLTL}$ property φ and their corresponding set of CHCs $\Pi(TS, \varphi)$. Our abstraction technique is based on *implicit predicate abstraction* [9].

Definition 3. *Let $\pi \in \Pi(TS, \varphi)$ be a normalized CHC of the following form $\bigwedge_{i=1}^n P_i(X') \wedge \delta(X, X') \rightarrow H(X)$, over a set of uninterpreted predicates P^U . Let $\mathbb{P} = \{\rho_1, \dots, \rho_m\}$ be a set of predicates, where ρ_i is a Σ -formula for $1 \leq i \leq m$, $B = \{b_1, \dots, b_m\}$ a set of fresh Boolean variables, and B' consists of the primed variants of B . Let $\{\hat{P} \mid P \in P^U\}$ be a set of uninterpreted predicates over B . The abstraction of π w.r.t. \mathbb{P} and B is defined by the function α s.t.*

$$\alpha(\pi, \mathbb{P}) := \bigwedge_{i=1}^n \hat{P}_i(B') \wedge \bigwedge_{j=1}^m (b'_j \leftrightarrow \rho_j(X')) \wedge \bigwedge_{j=1}^m (b_j \leftrightarrow \rho_j(X)) \wedge \delta(X, X') \rightarrow \hat{H}(B)$$

Given a set of predicates \mathbb{P} , applying the abstraction to $\Pi(TS, \varphi)$ results in the set $\Pi_{\mathbb{P}}(TS, \varphi) := \alpha(\Pi(TS, \varphi), \mathbb{P}) = \{\alpha(\pi, \mathbb{P}) \mid \pi \in \Pi(TS, \varphi)\}$. Note that CHCs in $\Pi_{\mathbb{P}}(TS, \varphi)$ are over a new set of uninterpreted predicates ($\hat{P}(B)$ instead of $P(X)$). Moreover, the set of variables $X \cup X' \cup B \cup B'$ is bound by universal quantifiers in all CHCs. From this point on, we omit TS and φ and refer to $\Pi(TS, \varphi)$ and $\Pi_{\mathbb{P}}(TS, \varphi)$ as Π and $\Pi_{\mathbb{P}}$, respectively.

Example 2. Assume $\mathbb{P} = \{x^1 = x^2\}$ and $B = \{b_1\}$. Consider the second CHC *rule*_{1} from Figure 1. Then $\alpha(\pi_2, \mathbb{P})$ is of the form:

$$\bigwedge_M \hat{D}_M(b'_1) \wedge (b'_1 \leftrightarrow x^{1'} = x'^2) \wedge (b_1 \leftrightarrow x^1 = x^2) \wedge \text{Tr}^1(\mathcal{V}^1, \mathcal{V}^{1'}) \wedge x^2 = x'^2 \wedge y^2 = y'^2 \rightarrow \hat{D}_{\{1\}}(b_1)$$

Procedure 1 HyAbsRefine(TS, φ, gen)

```
1:  $\Pi \leftarrow \text{DoomEncoding}(TS, \varphi)$ 
2:  $\mathbb{P} \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
3: while true do
4:    $\Pi_{\mathbb{P}} \leftarrow \alpha(\Pi, \mathbb{P})$ 
5:    $res \leftarrow \text{SOLVE}(\Pi_{\mathbb{P}})$ 
6:   if  $res = \text{sat}$  then
7:     return  $TS \models \varphi$ 
8:   else if  $res = \text{unsat}$  then
9:     Get unsat proof  $G = (V, E, r, L_F, L_S)$ 
10:     $\Pi_R \leftarrow \text{CHCRefinement}(G)$ 
11:     $res \leftarrow \text{Solve}(\Pi_R)$ 
12:    if  $res = \text{unsat}$  then
13:      return  $TS \not\models \varphi$ 
14:    else
15:      Get interpretation  $\mathcal{I} \models \Pi_R$ 
16:       $P_I \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
17:      for all  $v \in V$  do
18:         $P_I \leftarrow P_I \cup \text{Atoms}(\mathcal{I}(I_v))$ 
19:      end for
20:      if  $\text{gen} = \text{true}$  then
21:         $P_I \leftarrow P_I \cup \text{GenPreds}(G, \mathcal{I}, \mathbb{P}, P_I)$ 
22:      end if
23:       $\mathbb{P} \leftarrow \mathbb{P} \cup P_I$ 
24:    end if
25:  end if
26: end while
```

Procedure 2 GenPreds($G, \mathcal{I}, \mathbb{P}, P_I$)

```
1:  $P_g \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
2: for all  $v \in V$  do
3:    $P_g \leftarrow P_g \cup \text{Generalize}(\text{Atoms}(\mathcal{I}(I_v)))$ 
4: end for
5: if  $P_g = \emptyset$  then
6:   return  $\emptyset$ 
7: end if
8: sort  $P_g$  into levels:  $P_g^{(1)}, \dots, P_g^{(m)}$ 
9:  $C \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
10: for  $i = 1 \rightarrow m$  do
11:    $C \leftarrow C \cup P_g^{(i)}$ 
12:    $\hat{\Pi}_R \leftarrow \text{AbsCHCRefine}(G, \mathbb{P} \cup P_I \cup C)$ 
13:    $res \leftarrow \text{SOLVE}(\hat{\Pi}_R)$ 
14:   Get interpretation  $\mathcal{I}_R$ 
15:    $R \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
16:   for all  $v \in V$  do
17:      $R \leftarrow R \cup \text{Atoms}(\mathcal{I}_R(I_v))$ 
18:   end for
19:   if  $R \cap C \neq \emptyset$  then
20:     return  $R \cap C$ 
21:   end if
22: end for
23: return  $\emptyset$ 
```

The above abstraction function is used in the abstraction-refinement procedure that appears in Procedure 1. It starts by first encoding the verification problem of a $\forall^* \exists^*$ -OHyperLTL property φ w.r.t. a transition system TS using the method from [23] and initializes the set of predicates \mathbb{P} to be empty (lines 1-2). At each iteration of the abstraction-refinement loop, the procedure first generates the abstract set of CHCs $\Pi_{\mathbb{P}}$ using the method described above (line 4). If $\Pi_{\mathbb{P}}$ is satisfiable then the procedure terminates, concluding $TS \models \varphi$ (line 7).

If $\Pi_{\mathbb{P}}$ is UNSAT, an abstract counterexample is found. Note that since the set of CHCs is non-linear, the counterexample is represented by a proof in the form of a DAG (see Definition 1). Therefore, in order to check if the counterexample is spurious, the proof G is used to create a new set of *non-recursive* CHCs for refinement Π_R (see Definition 4 below) (line 10). If Π_R is UNSAT, the counterexample is real and the procedure terminates (line 13). Otherwise, there exists a satisfying interpretation $\mathcal{I} \models \Pi_R$. The interpretation is used to compute predicates that are needed for refinement (lines 16-23). Namely, for each uninterpreted predicate I_v that appears in Π_R , the atoms of $\mathcal{I}(I_v)$ are added to a set of refinement predicates P_I . In case the parameter gen is set to true, the collected predicates in P_I are generalized further using GenPreds (Procedure 2). A new iteration then begins using the updated set of predicates.

In the remainder of this section we describe the translation of the hyper-resolution proof produced by the CHC solver into Π_R , and the generation of predicates for refinement, deferring the generalization of refinement predicates (lines 20-22) to Section 4.

3.1 Hyper-Resolution Proof to CHCs

Assume that $\Pi_{\mathbb{P}}$ is unsatisfiable and let $G = (V, E, r, L_S, L_F)$ be the corresponding hyper-resolution proof for $\Pi_{\mathbb{P}}$. Intuitively, one can view the proof G as an “unrolling” of $\Pi_{\mathbb{P}}$ up to some bound n . In the context of $\forall^*\exists^*$ -OHyperLTL verification, the proof G represents a counterexample in the shape of a DAG.

Example 3. Consider our running example (Figure 1). When $\mathbb{P} = \{x^1 = x^2\}$ the abstraction is too coarse and a spurious counterexample exists. A fragment of the proof, which represents the counterexample, appears in Figure 2. The nodes u_1, u_2 and u_3 represent all possible choices for a schedule M after F_1 makes a step (represented by the nodes ℓ and v).

We now describe the fragment in Figure 2 in more detail. Let $G_{\Pi_{\mathbb{P}}} = (V, E, L_S, L_F)$ be the hyper-resolution proof for $\Pi_{\mathbb{P}}$. Recall that $\mathbb{P} = \{x_1 = x_2\}$ and hence $B = \{b_1\}$ (since there is only one predicate). Figure 2 captures a sub-graph of G , which represents one application of HYPERRES. For every node in Figure 2, the name of the node appears above the line. Let u be a node, the formula under the line represents the value of the labeling function $L_F(u)$, while the value given to b_1 by the substitution assigned to u (i.e. $L_S(u)$) appears in brackets.

The premise for applying HYPERRES is represented by the nodes u_1, u_2, u_3 and l , while node v represents the consequence. Note that each u_i , for $1 \leq i \leq 3$ resolves with a predicate that appears in the body of $\alpha(\text{rule}_{\{1\}}, \mathbb{P})$. Recall that:

$$\text{rule}_{\{1\}} = \bigwedge_{M'} D_{M'}(X') \wedge \delta_{\{1\}}(X, X') \rightarrow D_{\{1\}}(X)$$

and therefore

$$\alpha(\text{rule}_{\{1\}}, \mathbb{P}) = \bigwedge_{M'} D_{M'}(b'_1) \wedge (b'_1 \leftrightarrow x'^1 = x'^2) \wedge (b_1 \leftrightarrow x^1 = x^2) \wedge \delta_{\{1\}}(X, X') \rightarrow D_{\{1\}}(b_1)$$

Since $\hat{D}_{\{1\}}$ appears in the head of that $\alpha(\text{rule}_{\{1\}}, \mathbb{P})$, it is the consequence of HYPERRES. Moreover, this sub-graph represents a transition from $pc^1 = 2$ to $pc'^1 = 1$ in P_1 and from $pc^2 = 2$ to $pc'^2 = 1$ in P_2 . As a result, the value of the predicate is \perp before and after the transition.

In order to check if G represents a real or spurious counterexample, we construct a new *non-recursive* set of CHCs Π_R , which mirrors the structure of G . Using the “unrolling” analogy again, G demonstrates how CHCs in $\Pi_{\mathbb{P}}$ derive \perp . However, since G is generated w.r.t. the abstract CHCs, we need to try constructing a similarly structured proof using the concrete CHCs from Π . This attempt is captured by Π_R .

We consider two abstraction-refinement paradigms: *counterexample guided abstraction-refinement* (CEGAR) [10], which aims to eliminate the counterexample represented by G ; and *proof-based* abstraction (PBAR) [26], which aims to eliminate all counterexamples whose structure is similar to G . For each of these paradigms, the resulting Π_R has the same overall structure.

$$pc^1 = 1, pc^2 = 1$$

Fig. 2: A proof fragment.

Definition 4 (Refinement CHCs). Assume $\Pi_{\mathbb{P}}$ is UNSAT and let $G = (V, E, r, L_S, L_F)$ be the proof. Let $P^V = \{I_v \mid v \in V_I\}$ be a set of uninterpreted predicates over B . Let γ be a constraining function such that for all σ , in the case of PBAR $\gamma(X, B, \sigma) := \top$, otherwise, in the case of CEGAR $\gamma(X, B, \sigma) := \bigwedge_{j=1}^m ((b_j[\sigma] \leftrightarrow \rho_j(X)))$. The Refinement CHCs of G is defined as $\Pi_R(G, \gamma) = \{\forall X, X' \cdot \pi_v \mid v \in V_I\}$ where:

1. (Fact) For a node $v \in V_I \setminus \{r\}$ s.t. $L_F(\text{in}_T(v)) = \eta(X) \wedge \bigwedge_{j=1}^m (b_j \leftrightarrow \rho_j(X)) \rightarrow \hat{H}(B)$ define $\pi_v := \gamma(X, B, L_S(v)) \wedge \eta(X) \rightarrow I_v(X)$
2. (Rule) For a node $v \in V_I \setminus \{r\}$ s.t.

$$L_F(\text{in}_T(v)) = \bigwedge_{i=1}^n \hat{P}_i(B') \wedge \bigwedge_{j=1}^m ((b'_j \leftrightarrow \rho_j(X')) \wedge (b_j \leftrightarrow \rho_j(X))) \wedge \delta(X, X') \rightarrow \hat{H}(B)$$

$$\text{define } \pi_v := \bigwedge_{u \in \text{in}(v) \setminus \{\text{in}_T(v)\}} I_u(X') \wedge \gamma(X', B', L_S(v)) \wedge \gamma(X, B, L_S(v)) \wedge \delta(X, X') \rightarrow I_v(X)$$

3. (Query) For the root r , s.t. $L_F(\text{in}_T(r)) = \bigwedge_{i=1}^n \hat{P}_i(B) \wedge \bigwedge_{j=1}^m (b_j \leftrightarrow \rho_j(X)) \wedge \eta(X) \rightarrow \perp$ define $\pi_r := \bigwedge_{u \in \text{in}(r) \setminus \{\text{in}_T(r)\}} I_u(X) \wedge \gamma(X, B, L_S(r)) \wedge \eta(X) \rightarrow \perp$

Note that in the case of CEGAR, γ constrains the values X can take by using the values that the corresponding substitution (e.g. $L_S(v)$) assigns to the abstract Boolean variables in B .

Example 4. Consider the proof fragment that appears in Figure 2. Then, the corresponding CHC that is added to Π_R has one of the following forms. In the case of PBAR

$$\bigwedge_{i=0}^2 I_{u_i}(\mathcal{V}^1, \mathcal{V}^2) \wedge \text{Tr}^1(\mathcal{V}^1, \mathcal{V}^1) \wedge x^2 = x'^2 \wedge y^2 = y'^2 \rightarrow I_v(\mathcal{V}^1, \mathcal{V}^2)$$

while in the case of CEGAR, since $\sigma(b_1) = \perp$ and $\sigma(b'_1) = \perp$, then:

$$\bigwedge_{i=0}^2 I_{u_i}(\mathcal{V}^1, \mathcal{V}^2) \wedge x^{i1} \neq x'^2 \wedge x^1 \neq x^2 \wedge Tr^1(\mathcal{V}^1, \mathcal{V}^1) \wedge x^2 = x'^2 \wedge y^2 = y'^2 \rightarrow I_v(\mathcal{V}^1, \mathcal{V}^2)$$

Our goal is to check if a proof, similar in structure to G , also exists for Π . Therefore, the CHCs in Π_R are defined according to G . Namely, every uninterpreted predicate I_v in Π_R and every CHC $\pi \in \Pi_R$ correspond to an internal node $v \in V_I$ and to a terminal node $v \in V_T$, respectively. Moreover, the abstraction is removed, and CHCs in Π_R refer to the concrete set of variables X and X' . Since Π_R mirrors the structure of G , which is a DAG, the resulting set of CHCs is non-recursive (i.e. has no cycles). As a result, if Π_R is also UNSAT, then a proof with a similar structure to G exists for Π . In the context of $\forall^*\exists^*$ -OHyperLTL verification, this means a real counterexample exists.

Lemma 1. *Let Π be an unsatisfiable set of CHCs, and $G_\Pi = (V, E, r, L_S, L_F)$ a hyper-resolution proof of unsatisfiability for Π . The following holds:*

- For every $v \in V_I \setminus \{r\}$, if $in(v) \subseteq V_T$ then $in(v) = \{in_T(v)\}$ and $L_F(in_T(v)) = \forall X \cdot \varphi(X) \rightarrow H(X)$ (i.e. Fact).
- Otherwise, for every $v \in V_I \setminus \{r\}$ if $|in(v)| > 1$, then $L_F(in_T(v)) = \bigwedge_{i=1}^n P_i(X') \wedge \delta(X, X') \rightarrow H(X)$ (i.e. Rule).
- For the root r , $L_F(in_T(r)) = \bigwedge_{i=1}^n P_i(X) \wedge \eta(X) \rightarrow \perp$ (i.e. Query).

The above lemma follows from the structure of the CHCs.

Theorem 2. *Assume $\Pi_{\mathbb{P}}$ is UNSAT and let G be the corresponding hyper-resolution proof. If Π is SAT then $\Pi_R(G, \gamma)$ is SAT when γ is defined as above.*

Proof (Sketch). Π is SAT, thus there exists a Σ -interpretation \mathcal{I} which is a solution for Π . We define the Σ -interpretation \mathcal{I}' that assigns values for $P^V = \{I_v \mid v \in V_I\}$ in $\Pi_R(G, \xi)$, as follows: $\forall v \in V_I : \mathcal{I}'(I_v) = \mathcal{I}(P_i)$, where $L_F(v) = P_i(B)[L_S(v)]$. We will show that \mathcal{I}' is a solution for $\Pi_R(G, \xi)$.

1. $\forall v \in V_I \setminus \{r\}$ such that $in(v) = \{in_T(v)\}$, it holds that:

$$\mathcal{I}'(\pi_v) := \eta(X) \wedge \xi(X, B, L_S(v)) \rightarrow \mathcal{I}(I_v)$$

Let $\pi := \eta(X) \rightarrow H(X)$ be a CHC in Π such that $\alpha(\pi, \mathbb{P}) = L_F(in_T(v))$. Given that $\mathcal{I} \models_{\mathcal{T}} \Pi$, we know that $\mathcal{I}(\pi) := \eta(X) \rightarrow \mathcal{I}(H(X))$ is \mathcal{T} -valid. Hence, $\mathcal{I}'(\pi_v)$ is \mathcal{T} -valid.

2. $\forall v \in V_I \setminus \{r\}$ such that $|in(v)| > 1$, it holds: $\mathcal{I}'(\pi_v) := \bigwedge_{u \in in(v)} \mathcal{I}'(I_u(X')) \wedge \xi(X', B', L_S(v)) \wedge \xi(X, B, L_S(v)) \wedge \delta(X, X') \rightarrow \mathcal{I}'(I_v(X))$. Let

$$\pi := \bigwedge_{u \in in(v) \setminus \{in_T(v)\}} P_i(X') \wedge \delta(X, X') \rightarrow H(X)$$

be a CHC in Π such that $\alpha(\pi, \mathbb{P}) = L_F(in_T(v))$. Given that $\mathcal{I} \models_{\mathcal{T}} \Pi$, we know that $\mathcal{I}(\pi) := \bigwedge_{u \in in(v)} \mathcal{I}(P_i(X')) \wedge \delta(X, X') \rightarrow \mathcal{I}(H(X))$ is \mathcal{T} -valid. Hence, $\mathcal{I}'(\pi_v)$ is \mathcal{T} -valid.

3. For the root r : $\mathcal{I}'(\pi_r) := \bigwedge_{u \in \text{in}(r)} \mathcal{I}'(I_u(X)) \wedge \xi(X, B, L_S(v)) \wedge \eta(X) \rightarrow \perp$.
Let

$$\pi := \bigwedge_{u \in \text{in}(v) \setminus \{\text{in}_T(v)\}} P_i(X) \wedge \eta(X) \rightarrow \perp$$

be a CHC in Π such that $\alpha(\pi, \mathbb{P}) = L_F(\text{in}_T(v))$. Given that $\mathcal{I} \models_{\mathcal{T}} \Pi$, we know that $\mathcal{I}(\pi) := \bigwedge_{u \in \text{in}(v)} \mathcal{I}(P_i(X)) \wedge \eta(X) \rightarrow \perp$ is \mathcal{T} -valid. Hence, $\mathcal{I}'(\pi_v)$ is \mathcal{T} -valid.

We showed that $\mathcal{I}'(\pi_v)$ is \mathcal{T} -valid for every $\pi_v \in \Pi_R(G, \xi)$, i.e. $\Pi_R(G, \xi)$ is SAT. \square

3.2 Generating Predicates with Refinement CHCs

The computation of predicates for refinement appears in Procedure 1 (lines 16-23). First, predicates are extracted from the formulae associated with each uninterpreted predicate in Π_R and stored in the set P_I (lines 17-19). If the parameter *gen* is set to true (line 20), the generalization procedure **GenPreds** is called, possibly updating P_I . We discuss the generalization of predicates in the following section (Section 4). Lastly, P_I is added to the set of predicates \mathbb{P} and refinement is complete (line 23).

When generalization is not applied, the refinement procedure in **HyAbsRefine** is, intuitively, similar to interpolation-based refinement [20,24,2,34]. More precisely, if a counterexample is proved to be spurious, the satisfying interpretation \mathcal{I} for Π_R “summarizes” the facts that prove why the counterexample is spurious and provides details about a possible refinement. Using the predicates that appear in \mathcal{I} is sufficient to eliminate the spurious counterexample from the abstract model, and progress is achieved.

Theorem 3. *Assume $\Pi_{\mathbb{P}}$ is UNSAT and let G be the corresponding hyper-resolution proof. In addition, assume \mathcal{I} is a satisfying interpretation for $\Pi_R(G, \gamma)$. Let $\mathbb{P}' = \mathbb{P} \cup \bigcup_{v \in V} \text{Atoms}(\mathcal{I}(I_v))$. If $\Pi_{\mathbb{P}'}$ is UNSAT, then for every possible hyper-resolution proof of unsatisfiability G' for $\Pi_{\mathbb{P}'}$ it holds that $G' \neq G$.*

Proof (Sketch, Theorem 3).

Let us denote by $\mathbb{P}' = \mathbb{P} \cup \{\rho_{m+1}, \dots, \rho_q\}$ the set of predicates after refinement. In addition we denote by $\hat{B} := B \cup \{b_{m+1}, \dots, b_q\}$ the set of Boolean variables for \mathbb{P}' .

Next, assume by contradiction that there exists a hyper resolution proof of unsatisfiability G' for $\Pi_{\mathbb{P}'}$ such that G has the same structure as G' (i.e. $V = V'$ and $E = E'$) and for every $v \in V$ it holds that $L_S(v)$ and $L'_S(v)$ agree on variables in $X \cup X' \cup B \cup B'$.

Let v be a node in G and let $\sigma'_v = L'_S(v)$ be the substitution mapped to v in G' . Recall that σ'_v agrees with $L_S(v)$ on the variables in $X \cup X' \cup B \cup B'$. We now prove that G' is also a proof of unsatisfiability for Π_R . First, we prove by induction on the structure of G' that $\sigma'_v \models \mathcal{I}(I_v)$.

- Base: Let $v \in V'_I$ be an internal node such that $in(v) = \{in_T(v)\}$. In this case, according to Lemma 2: $L'_F(in_T(v))$ is of the form: $\eta(X) \wedge \bigwedge_{j=1}^q (b_j \leftrightarrow \rho_j(X)) \rightarrow \hat{H}(\hat{B})$. From Definition 1 we know that $\sigma'_v \models \eta(X) \wedge \bigwedge_{j=1}^q (b_j \leftrightarrow \rho_j(X))$. Moreover, since \mathcal{I} is a solution to Π_R we know that $\eta(X) \wedge \xi(X, B, \sigma) \rightarrow \mathcal{I}(I_v)$, where $\sigma = L_S(v)$ is valid. Recall that σ'_v agrees with σ on $X \cup X' \cup B \cup B'$. As a result, it follows that $\sigma'_v \models \xi(X, B, L_S(v))$. Hence, we get that $\sigma'_v \models \mathcal{I}(I_v)$.
- Step: Let $v \in V_I$ where $|in(v)| > 1$. By the induction hypothesis we get that $\forall u \in in(v) \setminus \{in_T(v)\} : \sigma'_u \models \mathcal{I}(I_u)$. Moreover, in this case, $L'_F(in_T(v))$ is of the form:

$$\bigwedge_{i=1}^n \hat{P}_i(B') \wedge \bigwedge_{j=1}^q ((b'_j \leftrightarrow \rho_j(X')) \wedge (b_j \leftrightarrow \rho_j(X))) \wedge \delta(X, X') \rightarrow \hat{H}(B)$$

Again, following Definition 1 we have that $\sigma'_v \models \bigwedge_{j=1}^q ((b'_j \leftrightarrow \rho_j(X')) \wedge (b_j \leftrightarrow \rho_j(X))) \wedge \delta(X, X')$. Next, given \mathcal{I} is a solution to Π_R we have that:

$$\bigwedge_{u \in in(v) \setminus \{in_T(v)\}} \mathcal{I}(I_u)(X') \wedge \xi(X', B', \sigma) \wedge \xi(X, B, \sigma) \wedge \delta(X, X') \rightarrow \mathcal{I}(I_v)(X)$$

where $\sigma = L_S(v)$. Following similar arguments to those of the base case it follows that $\sigma'_v \models \xi(X', B', \sigma) \wedge \xi(X, B, \sigma) \wedge \delta(X, X')$ and as a result, $\sigma'_v \models \mathcal{I}(I_v)$.

Lastly, using this claim, we get that for the root node r , where $L'_F(in_T(r))$ is of the form:

$$\bigwedge_{i=1}^n \hat{P}_i(B) \wedge \bigwedge_{j=1}^q (b_j \leftrightarrow \rho_j(X)) \wedge \eta(X) \rightarrow \perp$$

It holds that $\forall u \in in(r) \setminus \{in_T(r)\} : \sigma'_u \models \mathcal{I}(I_u)$. In addition, since σ'_u agrees with $\sigma_u = L_S(u)$ on $X \cup X' \cup B \cup B'$, we have that $\sigma'_u \models \bigwedge_{j=1}^q (b_j \leftrightarrow \rho_j(X)) \wedge \eta(X)$. This is a contradiction to the fact that the following formula is valid:

$$\bigwedge_{u \in in(r) \setminus \{in_T(r)\}} \mathcal{I}(I_u)(X) \wedge \xi(X, B, L_S(v)) \wedge \eta(X) \rightarrow \perp$$

□

It is important to note that Theorem 3 guarantees progress since it ensures that if a counterexample exists after refinement, the hyper-resolution proof must be different. Yet, there are subtle differences depending on the kind of refinement used. In the case of PBAR the structure of G and G' , namely the graph itself, is different. However, in the case of CEGAR, G and G' may have a similar structure (same graph) but then for a given node v , the substitutions $L_S(v)$ and $L'_S(v)$ must not agree on some variable. This means that G and G' represent different ground refutations.

4 Generalizing Predicates for Refinement

In this section we present the procedure that generalizes predicates during the refinement stage. We start by presenting a general procedure, followed by a specific implementation used for verification of $\forall^*\exists^*$ -OHyperLTL properties.

One known limitation of the refinement approach presented in the previous section is that the predicates used in \mathcal{I} may be “too specific” (since they may refer to specific states). This limitation may result in iterative refinement steps that fail to converge. In order to overcome this limitation, we suggest a more general framework that aims to *generalize* the predicates extracted from \mathcal{I} .

4.1 Generalizing Predicates

We now provide a high-level description of our suggested generalization procedure. The algorithm **GenPreds** appears in Procedure 2. It starts by iterating over all nodes of G . For each node v it calls the function **generalize**, which processes the atoms that appear in $\mathcal{I}(I_v)$ (line 3). For example, if a given $\mathcal{I}(I_v)$ includes the atoms $x_1 = 0$ and $x_2 = 0$, the generalization procedure may produce the predicate $x_1 = x_2$. Note that this predicate is a generalization of the two predicates since $(x_1 = 0 \wedge x_2 = 0) \rightarrow x_1 = x_2$. Next, **GenPreds** sorts the resulting set P_g into priority buckets using a pre-defined priority metric.

In the last phase, **GenPreds** iterates over the priority buckets. At the i -th iteration, a set of *abstract refinement CHCs* $\hat{\Pi}_R$ is created using the set of predicates $\mathbb{P} \cup P_I \cup \bigcup_{j=1}^i P_g^j$ in similar fashion to the procedure that appears in the beginning of Section 3. Unlike the set of CHCs Π_R , the uninterpreted predicates that appear in $\hat{\Pi}_R$ are over the predicates used for abstraction. Hence, the solver is “forced” to generate a satisfying interpretation that only uses the supplied set of predicates. If the generated interpretation includes generalized predicates, **GenPreds** terminates and returns these generalized predicates. Otherwise, it returns the empty set.

It is important to note that since **AbsCHCRefinement** is given $\mathbb{P} \cup P_I \cup C$, there must be a satisfying interpretation and the set $\hat{\Pi}_R$ cannot be UNSAT. This is due to the fact that $\mathbb{P} \cup P_I$ is already guaranteed to be precise enough in order to rule out the given spurious counterexample.

The extra solving phase over the abstract set of CHCs is used to sift through the set of generalized predicates and identify those that are useful, using the pre-defined priorities to decide the order in which sifting occurs. The abstract CHCs used for refinement are defined as follows:

Definition 5 (Abstract Refinement CHCs). *Let Π_R be a set of refinement CHCs with respect to $\Pi_{\mathbb{P}}$, where $\mathbb{P} = \{\rho_1, \dots, \rho_m\}$. Let $\mathbb{Q} = \mathbb{P} \uplus \{\rho_{m+1}, \dots, \rho_q\}$ and $\hat{B} = B \uplus \{b_{m+1}, \dots, b_q\}$ ($q > m$) be a set of predicates and corresponding Boolean variables, respectively. The abstract refinement CHCs of Π_R w.r.t. \mathbb{Q} is defined as $\hat{\Pi}_R := \alpha(\Pi_R, \mathbb{Q}) = \{\alpha(\pi, \mathbb{Q}) \mid \pi \in \Pi_R\}$.*

It is important to note that unlike Π_R , the set $\hat{\Pi}_R$ is in terms of the abstract Boolean variables \hat{B} . After solving the set of CHCs $\hat{\Pi}_R$, if the interpretation uses

any of the generalized predicates that appear in C , we conclude these are useful for refinement. Moreover, since they are a generalization of the predicates in P_I , they are more likely to rule-out more spurious counterexamples and hence allow `HyAbsRefine` to converge faster.

4.2 Learning Generalized Predicates for Hyperproperty Verification

Recall that hyperproperties refer to multiple traces of a transition system. Therefore, the invariants, schedulers, and witnesses (for existential quantifiers) often refer to states of the composed transition system. As a result, when considering predicate abstraction, it is natural that expressing, for example, an invariant requires relational predicates. Namely, predicates that relate state variables of different copies of the transition system.

The heuristic we use in our implementation tries to generate predicates that express equality between variables from different copies of the transition system. Let Π_R be the set of CHCs used for refinement and let \mathcal{I} be its satisfying interpretation. Our procedure analyzes the predicates in $Atoms(\mathcal{I}(I_v))$ and applies unification that generates possible generalized relational predicates.

Given the atoms $\rho_1 = (f_1 \text{ op}_1 g_1)$ and $\rho_2 = (f_2 \text{ op}_2 g_2)$, where $\text{op}_i \in \{=, \leq, \geq, <, >\}$, the unification of these two atoms is defined as:

$$\text{UNIFY}(\rho_1, \rho_2) = \begin{cases} g_1 = g_2, & \text{if } \text{op}_1 = \text{op}_2 \text{ and } f_1 = f_2, \text{Vars}(g_i) \neq \emptyset, i \in \{1, 2\} \\ f_1 = f_2, & \text{if } \text{op}_1 = \text{op}_2 \text{ and } g_1 = g_2, \text{Vars}(f_i) \neq \emptyset, i \in \{1, 2\} \\ \perp, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

In our implementation of Algorithm 2, the call to `Generalize` (line 3) iterates over pairs of predicates $\rho_1, \rho_2 \in Atoms(\mathcal{I}(I_v))$ and executes `UNIFY`(ρ_1, ρ_2).

Prioritized Predicate Selection. Our heuristic uses two priority levels: (i) high-priority for predicates that relate variables from different copies of the program and are syntactically concise; and (ii) low-priority for predicates that only refer to a single copy of a program or are syntactically complex. For instance, generalized predicates that include only single trace variables such as $(x_1 = y_1)$, which could be the unification of $(x_1 = c), (y_1 = c)$ for some constant c , are less effective for refinement in practice than predicates that are "relational", e.g. $(x_1 = x_2/4)$ which could be the unification of $(x_1 = c'), (x_2/4 = c')$ for some constant c' .

5 Experimental Evaluation

We implemented our automatic abstraction-refinement algorithm in a tool called `AbsHyHorn`³. The new tool is built on top of the existing `HyHorn` tool, which implements the reduction of $\forall^*\exists^*$ -OHyperLTL verification to CHC-SAT [23].

³ https://github.com/TechnionFV/hyperprops_as_chcs

<i>k</i> -safety	Concrete	PBAR				CEGAR			
		w/o gen	#P/#I	w gen	#P/#I	w/o gen	#P/#I	w gen	#P/#I
double square NI ff	–	–	–	10.03	19/2	–	–	–	–
double square NI ff (simp)	–	–	–	6.62	20/3	–	–	–	–
half square NI	0.29	6.15	14/2	17.71	34/3	4.11	11/2	4.14	11/2
squares sum	4.11	30.44	27/6	15.98	27/5	21.60	18/6	37.06	25/6
squares sum (simp)	0.20	205.40	31/9	197.51	33/8	126.38	16/6	19.14	13/6
array insert	–	168.56	53/4	178.97	54/4	140.40	24/4	500.79	31/8
array insert (simp)	–	62.05	44/2	110.1	52/2	–	–	–	–
explx3	0.08	1.52	6/2	1.71	8/3	1.15	4/2	1.15	4/2
col item symm	0.48	11.82	53/1	16.25	59/1	12.71	59/1	22.46	70/1
fig 2 from [6]	–	–	–	16.08	27/6	–	–	–	–
fig 3 from [13]	0.12	5.79	18/3	6.12	19/3	17.66	15/6	7.01	13/3
counter det	–	2.09	9/2	1.71	9/2	1.80	8/2	2.14	8/2
mult equiv	–	–	–	234.22	56/7	–	–	–	–
mult equiv (simp)	–	–	–	33.94	25/4	–	–	–	–
array int mod	–	–	–	619.22	91/4	–	–	–	–
div monotone	–	0.51	4/1	0.52	4/1	0.61	6/1	1.07	7/1
mult dist	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–

Table 1: Results for *k*-safety benchmarks. “–” indicates timeout.

AbsHyHorn is implemented on top of Z3 (4.12.0) [28] through its Python API, using SPACER [18,25] as a CHC solver. **AbsHyHorn** takes as input a program in the form of a CFG and a $\forall^*\exists^*$ -OHyperLTL property (following the format introduced in [6]). **AbsHyHorn** supports all first-order theories supported by SPACER. In our experiments, we used the theories of Linear Integer Arithmetic and Arrays.

The experimental evaluation compares two variants of **AbsHyHorn**, one that uses PBAR and another that uses CEGAR for refinement. Both these variants are compared against **HyHorn**, when applied to the concrete programs with no user-provided abstraction⁴.

For the benchmark, we adopt all examples from [23], which include many *k*-safety and liveness hyperproperties (such as Generalized Non-Interference) from the $\forall^*\exists^*$ -OHyperLTL fragment. In addition, two new benchmarks, which were not part of the original suite, are added—`div monotone` (monotonicity of integer division) for *k*-safety, and `sum nondet` for $\forall^*\exists^*$. In $\forall^*\exists^*$ benchmarks, when the transition relation has infinite branching as in the general case defined by [23], the restrictions were provided and encoded in the transition relation. All experiments were performed on a server that uses an AMD EPYC 74F3 CPU with 32GB of memory, with a timeout of 7200 seconds for each experiment.

Table 1 and Table 2 present the evaluation for *k*-safety and $\forall^*\exists^*$ hyperproperties, respectively. The time is reported in seconds. The columns with $\#P/\#I$ represent the number of predicates **AbsHyHorn** learns and the number of abstraction-refinement iterations it executes.

For *k*-safety benchmarks **AbsHyHorn** solves significantly more examples when compared to **HyHorn**. PBAR solves all of the benchmarks, except `mult dist` (a 3-safety property). When comparing PBAR against CEGAR, it is clear that PBAR performs better. One observation regarding this difference is that when using

⁴ Other tools for verification of $\forall^*\exists^*$ -OHyperLTL do not operate on the concrete program and require user-provided predicates. Hence, the comparison is only against **HyHorn**.

$\forall^*\exists^*$	Concrete	PBAR				CEGAR			
		w/o gen	#P/#I	w gen	#P/#I	w/o gen	#P/#I	w gen	#P/#I
counter negate	0.08	0.97	4/2	2.15	7/2	3.52	6/3	6.95	10/4
p1 simple	0.22	2.38	6/3	5.23	8/3	4.51	9/3	6.01	8/3
refine	0.12	1.09	3/1	1.07	3/1	1.63	3/1	1.61	3/1
refine 2	0.85	0.89	3/1	0.87	3/1	1.23	3/1	1.23	3/1
compiler opt 1	2.31	0.44	2/1	0.41	2/1	0.65	2/1	0.65	2/1
compiler opt 2	0.20	1.54	8/2	2.89	9/2	5.13	8/3	19.16	15/4
sum nondet	–	21.26	15/3	35.17	16/3	–	–	–	–
smaller	–	0.54	2/1	0.53	2/1	0.44	2/1	0.43	2/1
async gni	0.34	16.57	7/3	16.29	7/3	8.79	4/3	8.81	4/3
P1 (GNI)	0.18	2.14	4/1	5.47	4/1	2.32	4/1	4.04	5/1
P2 (GNI)	6.85	298.63	8/2	–	–	–	–	–	–
P3 (GNI)	0.15	3.52	5/1	9.88	7/1	3.76	5/1	6.91	6/1
P4 (GNI)	0.67	5.47	5/1	9.75	6/1	5.94	5/1	9.77	6/1
counter sum	0.15	14.85	16/3	37.10	17/3	–	–	53.91	13/5
counter diff	–	6.74	5/2	–	–	–	–	48.08	11/5

Table 2: Results for $\forall^*\exists^*$ benchmarks. “–” indicates timeout.

CEGAR, **AbsHyHorn** learns predicates that are “too specific”, eliminating only one counterexample at each iteration. In contrast, when using PBAR, most of the extracted predicates are relational (relating variables from different program traces). For the $\forall^*\exists^*$ benchmarks, **AbsHyHorn** with PBAR solves all the examples, while when using CEGAR it is outperformed by **HyHorn**. The main reason for this behavior is that most of these examples are very simple. Hence, in most cases, the abstraction-refinement loop only adds an overhead. This also explains why in this case, using the predicate generalization technique (Section 4) is not particularly helpful.

6 Related Work

There exists a large body of work on verification of hyperproperties [32,15,35,5,30,14,33,6,23,12]. However, to the best of our knowledge, there is no previous work that performs automatic abstraction-refinement for a comprehensive fragment of hyperproperties, such as $\forall^*\exists^*$ -OHyperLTL. Previous works either use a fixed, user-given abstraction, or implement abstraction-refinement for a user-given self-composed system [32] and limited to k -safety hyperproperties only.

The work that is closest to ours is [31], where the authors suggest an abstraction-refinement algorithm for k -safety properties. However, unlike our algorithm the work in [31] is based on [30], where the alignment is pre-determined and verification is executed on a self-composition of the program/system. As a result, if the alignment that was chosen to encode the self-composed system is incorrect, abstraction-refinement never terminates. Since our algorithm extends the more general CHC-based approach of [23], in the case of k -safety it searches for the alignment, relational invariant and the abstraction, simultaneously. Moreover, **HyAbsRefine** supports the entire $\forall^*\exists^*$ -OHyperLTL fragment, and is not limited to k -safety only. The work in [35] also uses abstraction-refinement, but is limited only to information-flow properties, and like [30,31] operates on a fixed self-composed program.

For refinement, our algorithm formalizes and uses CHCs. It transforms a DAG hyper-resolution proof into non-recursive set of CHCs. Intuitively, this is similar to tree/DAG-interpolation refinement [19,27,29,1,3]. However, unlike the interpolation-based approaches, our CHC-based refinement does not require an explicit expansion of the DAG neither into a tree nor sequences. This fact avoids the complexity that such an expansion incurs. Moreover, if the underlying CHC solver is not based on interpolation (SPACER, like in our implementation), this expansion does not happen implicitly by the solver.

7 Conclusions and Future Work

We present `HyAbsRefine`, an automatic abstraction-refinement algorithm for verification of $\forall^*\exists^*$ -OHyperLTL hyperproperties. Our refinement approach is based on a transformation of a DAG counterexample to a non-recursive, non-linear set of CHCs. When the refinement CHCs are solved, new predicates are derived from their satisfying interpretation. Our evaluation shows that $\forall^*\exists^*$ -OHyperLTL is able to synthesize the relational predicates that are required in order to solve all benchmarks in our set, but one. We emphasize that `HyAbsRefine` achieves this without any user-given predicates.

As a future work, we intend to extend this algorithm to support transition systems with infinite branching, without requiring restrictions that are encoded into the transition relation a priori.

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References

1. Albarghouthi, A.: Software Verification with Program-Graph Interpolation and Abstraction. Ph.D. thesis, University of Toronto, Canada (2015), <http://hdl.handle.net/1807/69199>
2. Albarghouthi, A., Gurfinkel, A., Chechik, M.: Craig interpretation. In: Miné, A., Schmidt, D. (eds.) Static Analysis - 19th International Symposium, SAS 2012, Deauville, France, September 11-13, 2012. Proceedings. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 7460, pp. 300–316. Springer (2012)
3. Asadi, S., Blich, M., Hyvärinen, A.E.J., Fedyukovich, G., Sharygina, N.: Farkas-based tree interpolation. In: Pichardie, D., Sighireanu, M. (eds.) Static Analysis - 27th International Symposium, SAS 2020, Virtual Event, November 18-20, 2020, Proceedings. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 12389, pp. 357–379. Springer (2020)

4. Ball, T., Majumdar, R., Millstein, T.D., Rajamani, S.K.: Automatic predicate abstraction of C programs. In: Burke, M., Soffa, M.L. (eds.) Proceedings of the 2001 ACM SIGPLAN Conference on Programming Language Design and Implementation (PLDI), Snowbird, Utah, USA, June 20-22, 2001. pp. 203–213. ACM (2001)
5. Barthe, G., Gaboardi, M., Hsu, J.: Relational verification using product programs. *Journal of the ACM (JACM)* **65**(1), 1–49 (2018)
6. Beutner, R., Finkbeiner, B.: Software verification of hyperproperties beyond k-safety. In: Shoham, S., Vizel, Y. (eds.) Computer Aided Verification - 34th International Conference, CAV 2022, Haifa, Israel, August 7-10, 2022, Proceedings, Part I. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 13371, pp. 341–362. Springer (2022). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-13185-1_17, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-13185-1_17
7. Bjørner, N.S., Gurfinkel, A., McMillan, K.L., Rybalchenko, A.: Horn clause solvers for program verification. In: Beklemishev, L.D., Blass, A., Dershowitz, N., Finkbeiner, B., Schulte, W. (eds.) Fields of Logic and Computation II - Essays Dedicated to Yuri Gurevich on the Occasion of His 75th Birthday. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 9300, pp. 24–51. Springer (2015). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-23534-9_2, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-23534-9_2
8. Blichla, M., Britikov, K., Sharygina, N.: The golem horn solver. In: Enea, C., Lal, A. (eds.) Computer Aided Verification - 35th International Conference, CAV 2023, Paris, France, July 17-22, 2023, Proceedings, Part II. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 13965, pp. 209–223. Springer (2023)
9. Cimatti, A., Griggio, A., Mover, S., Tonetta, S.: IC3 modulo theories via implicit predicate abstraction. *CoRR* **abs/1310.6847** (2013), <http://arxiv.org/abs/1310.6847>
10. Clarke, E.M., Grumberg, O., Jha, S., Lu, Y., Veith, H.: Counterexample-guided abstraction refinement for symbolic model checking. *J. ACM* **50**(5), 752–794 (2003). <https://doi.org/10.1145/876638.876643>, <https://doi.org/10.1145/876638.876643>
11. Clarkson, M.R., Schneider, F.B.: Hyperproperties. *J. Comput. Secur.* **18**(6), 1157–1210 (2010). <https://doi.org/10.3233/JCS-2009-0393>, <https://doi.org/10.3233/JCS-2009-0393>
12. Cousot, P., Wang, J.: Calculational design of hyperlogics by abstract interpretation. *Proc. ACM Program. Lang.* **9**(POPL), 446–478 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3704852>, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3704852>
13. Farzan, A., Vandikas, A.: Automated hypersafety verification. In: Dillig, I., Tasiran, S. (eds.) Computer Aided Verification – 31st International Conference, CAV 2019, New York City, NY, USA, July 15–18, 2019, Proceedings, Part I. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 11561, pp. 200–218. Springer (2019)
14. Finkbeiner, B.: Model checking algorithms for hyperproperties (invited paper). In: Henglein, F., Shoham, S., Vizel, Y. (eds.) Verification, Model Checking, and Abstract Interpretation - 22nd International Conference, VMCAI 2021, Copenhagen, Denmark, January 17-19, 2021, Proceedings. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 12597, pp. 3–16. Springer (2021)
15. Finkbeiner, B., Hahn, C., Stenger, M.: Hyperproperty model checking. In: Computer Aided Verification (CAV). pp. 200–214. Springer (2015)
16. Flanagan, C., Qadeer, S.: Predicate abstraction for software verification. In: Launchbury, J., Mitchell, J.C. (eds.) Conference Record of POPL 2002: The 29th SIGPLAN-SIGACT Symposium on Principles of Programming Languages, Portland, OR, USA, January 16-18, 2002. pp. 191–202. ACM (2002). <https://doi.org/10.1145/503272.503291>, <https://doi.org/10.1145/503272.503291>

17. Graf, S., Saïdi, H.: Construction of abstract state graphs with PVS. In: Grumberg, O. (ed.) *Computer Aided Verification, 9th International Conference, CAV '97*, Haifa, Israel, June 22-25, 1997, Proceedings. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 1254, pp. 72–83. Springer (1997). https://doi.org/10.1007/3-540-63166-6_10, https://doi.org/10.1007/3-540-63166-6_10
18. Gurfinkel, A.: Program verification with constrained horn clauses (invited paper). In: *Computer Aided Verification – 34th International Conference, CAV 2022*, Haifa, Israel, August 7–10, 2022, Proceedings, Part I. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 13371, pp. 19–29. Springer (2022)
19. Heizmann, M., Hoenicke, J., Podelski, A.: Nested interpolants. In: Hermenegildo, M.V., Palsberg, J. (eds.) *Proceedings of the 37th ACM SIGPLAN-SIGACT Symposium on Principles of Programming Languages, POPL 2010*, Madrid, Spain, January 17-23, 2010. pp. 471–482. ACM (2010). <https://doi.org/10.1145/1706299.1706353>, <https://doi.org/10.1145/1706299.1706353>
20. Henzinger, T.A., Jhala, R., Majumdar, R., McMillan, K.L.: Abstractions from proofs. In: Jones, N.D., Leroy, X. (eds.) *Proceedings of the 31st ACM SIGPLAN-SIGACT Symposium on Principles of Programming Languages, POPL 2004*, Venice, Italy, January 14-16, 2004. pp. 232–244. ACM (2004). <https://doi.org/10.1145/964001.964021>, <https://doi.org/10.1145/964001.964021>
21. Henzinger, T.A., Jhala, R., Majumdar, R., Sutre, G.: Lazy abstraction. In: Launchbury, J., Mitchell, J.C. (eds.) *Conference Record of POPL 2002: The 29th SIGPLAN-SIGACT Symposium on Principles of Programming Languages*, Portland, OR, USA, January 16-18, 2002. pp. 58–70. ACM (2002)
22. Hojjat, H., Rümmer, P.: The ELDARICA horn solver. In: Bjørner, N.S., Gurfinkel, A. (eds.) *2018 Formal Methods in Computer Aided Design, FMCAD 2018*, Austin, TX, USA, October 30 - November 2, 2018. pp. 1–7. IEEE (2018)
23. Itzhaky, S., Shoham, S., Vizel, Y.: Hyperproperty verification as CHC satisfiability. In: Weirich, S. (ed.) *Programming Languages and Systems - 33rd European Symposium on Programming, ESOP 2024*, Held as Part of the European Joint Conferences on Theory and Practice of Software, ETAPS 2024, Luxembourg City, Luxembourg, April 6-11, 2024, Proceedings, Part II. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 14577, pp. 212–241. Springer (2024). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-57267-8_9, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-57267-8_9
24. Jhala, R., McMillan, K.L.: A practical and complete approach to predicate refinement. In: Hermanns, H., Palsberg, J. (eds.) *Tools and Algorithms for the Construction and Analysis of Systems, 12th International Conference, TACAS 2006 Held as Part of the Joint European Conferences on Theory and Practice of Software, ETAPS 2006*, Vienna, Austria, March 25 - April 2, 2006, Proceedings. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 3920, pp. 459–473. Springer (2006)
25. Komuravelli, A., Gurfinkel, A., Chaki, S.: Smt-based model checking for recursive programs. In: Biere, A., Bloem, R. (eds.) *Computer Aided Verification - 26th International Conference, CAV 2014*, Held as Part of the Vienna Summer of Logic, VSL 2014, Vienna, Austria, July 18-22, 2014. Proceedings. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 8559, pp. 17–34. Springer (2014)
26. McMillan, K.L., Amla, N.: Automatic abstraction without counterexamples. In: Garavel, H., Hatchiff, J. (eds.) *Tools and Algorithms for the Construction and Analysis of Systems, 9th International Conference, TACAS 2003*, Held as Part of the Joint European Conferences on Theory and Practice of Software, ETAPS 2003, Warsaw, Poland, April 7-11, 2003, Proceedings. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 2619, pp. 2–17. Springer (2003)

27. McMillan, K.L., Rybalchenko, A.: Solving constrained horn clauses using interpolation (2013), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:123198987>
28. de Moura, L.M., Bjørner, N.: Z3: An efficient SMT solver. In: Tools and Algorithms for the Construction and Analysis of Systems, 14th International Conference, TACAS 2008, Held as Part of the Joint European Conferences on Theory and Practice of Software, ETAPS 2008, Budapest, Hungary, March 29–April 6, 2008. Proceedings. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 4963, pp. 337–340. Springer (2008)
29. Rümmer, P., Hojjat, H., Kuncak, V.: On recursion-free horn clauses and craig interpolation. *Formal Methods Syst. Des.* **47**(1), 1–25 (2015)
30. Shemer, R., Gurfinkel, A., Shoham, S., Vizel, Y.: Property directed self composition. CoRR **abs/1905.07705** (2019), <http://arxiv.org/abs/1905.07705>
31. Shenoy, A., S, S.P., Madhukar, K., Shemer, R., Srivas, M.K.: Automated property directed self composition. In: André, É., Sun, J. (eds.) Automated Technology for Verification and Analysis - 21st International Symposium, ATVA 2023, Singapore, October 24-27, 2023, Proceedings, Part II. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 14216, pp. 139–158. Springer (2023). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-45332-8_7, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-45332-8_7
32. Terauchi, T., Aiken, A.: Secure information flow as a safety problem. In: Static Analysis, 12th International Symposium, SAS 2005, London, UK, September 7-9, 2005, Proceedings. pp. 352–367 (2005). https://doi.org/10.1007/11547662_24, https://doi.org/10.1007/11547662_24
33. Unno, H., Terauchi, T., Koskinen, E.: Constraint-based relational verification. In: Silva, A., Leino, K.R.M. (eds.) Computer Aided Verification - 33rd International Conference, CAV 2021, Virtual Event, July 20-23, 2021, Proceedings, Part I. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 12759, pp. 742–766. Springer (2021). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-81685-8_35, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-81685-8_35
34. Wang, X., Anderson, G., Dillig, I., McMillan, K.L.: Learning abstractions for program synthesis. CoRR **abs/1804.04152** (2018), <http://arxiv.org/abs/1804.04152>
35. Yang, W., Vizel, Y., Subramanyan, P., Gupta, A., Malik, S.: Lazy self-composition for security verification. In: Chockler, H., Weissenbacher, G. (eds.) Computer Aided Verification - 30th International Conference, CAV 2018, Held as Part of the Federated Logic Conference, FloC 2018, Oxford, UK, July 14-17, 2018, Proceedings, Part II. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 10982, pp. 136–156. Springer (2018)

A Proofs

Lemma 2. *Let Π be an unsatisfiable set of CHCs, and $G_\Pi = (V, E, r, L_S, L_F)$ a hyper-resolution proof of unsatisfiability for Π . The following holds:*

- For every $v \in V_I \setminus \{r\}$, if $in(v) \subseteq V_T$ then $in(v) = \{in_T(v)\}$ and $L_F(in_T(v)) = \forall X \cdot \varphi(X) \rightarrow H(X)$ (i.e. Fact).
- Otherwise, for every $v \in V_I \setminus \{r\}$ if $|in(v)| > 1$, then $L_F(in_T(v)) = \bigwedge_{i=1}^n P_i(X') \wedge \delta(X, X') \rightarrow H(X)$ (i.e. Rule).
- For the root r , $L_F(in_T(r)) = \bigwedge_{i=1}^n P_i(X) \wedge \eta(X) \rightarrow \perp$ (i.e. Query).

The above lemma follows from the structure of the CHCs. Next, we prove Theorem 2 and Theorem 3.

Proof (Sketch, Theorem 2). Π is SAT, thus there exists a Σ -interpretation \mathcal{I} which is a solution for Π . We define the Σ -interpretation \mathcal{I}' that assigns values for $P^V = \{I_v \mid v \in V_I\}$ in $\Pi_R(G, \xi)$, as follows: $\forall v \in V_I : \mathcal{I}'(I_v) = \mathcal{I}(P_i)$, where $L_F(v) = \hat{P}_i(B)[L_S(v)]$. We will show that \mathcal{I}' is a *solution* for $\Pi_R(G, \xi)$.

1. $\forall v \in V_I \setminus \{r\}$ such that $in(v) = \{in_T(v)\}$, it holds that:

$$\mathcal{I}'(\pi_v) := \eta(X) \wedge \xi(X, B, L_S(v)) \rightarrow \mathcal{I}(I_v)$$

Let $\pi := \eta(X) \rightarrow H(X)$ be a CHC in Π such that $\alpha(\pi, \mathbb{P}) = L_F(in_T(v))$. Given that $\mathcal{I} \models_{\mathcal{T}} \Pi$, we know that $\mathcal{I}(\pi) := \eta(X) \rightarrow \mathcal{I}(H(X))$ is \mathcal{T} -valid. Hence, $\mathcal{I}'(\pi_v)$ is \mathcal{T} -valid.

2. $\forall v \in V_I \setminus \{r\}$ such that $|in(v)| > 1$, it holds: $\mathcal{I}'(\pi_v) := \bigwedge_{u \in in(v)} \mathcal{I}'(I_u(X')) \wedge \xi(X', B', L_S(v)) \wedge \xi(X, B, L_S(v)) \wedge \delta(X, X') \rightarrow \mathcal{I}'(I_v(X))$. Let

$$\pi := \bigwedge_{u \in in(v) \setminus \{in_T(v)\}} P_i(X') \wedge \delta(X, X') \rightarrow H(X)$$

be a CHC in Π such that $\alpha(\pi, \mathbb{P}) = L_F(in_T(v))$. Given that $\mathcal{I} \models_{\mathcal{T}} \Pi$, we know that $\mathcal{I}(\pi) := \bigwedge_{u \in in(v)} \mathcal{I}(P_i(X')) \wedge \delta(X, X') \rightarrow \mathcal{I}(H(X))$ is \mathcal{T} -valid. Hence, $\mathcal{I}'(\pi_v)$ is \mathcal{T} -valid.

3. For the root r : $\mathcal{I}'(\pi_r) := \bigwedge_{u \in in(r)} \mathcal{I}'(I_u(X)) \wedge \xi(X, B, L_S(v)) \wedge \eta(X) \rightarrow \perp$. Let

$$\pi := \bigwedge_{u \in in(v) \setminus \{in_T(v)\}} P_i(X) \wedge \eta(X) \rightarrow \perp$$

be a CHC in Π such that $\alpha(\pi, \mathbb{P}) = L_F(in_T(v))$. Given that $\mathcal{I} \models_{\mathcal{T}} \Pi$, we know that $\mathcal{I}(\pi) := \bigwedge_{u \in in(v)} \mathcal{I}(P_i(X)) \wedge \eta(X) \rightarrow \perp$ is \mathcal{T} -valid. Hence, $\mathcal{I}'(\pi_v)$ is \mathcal{T} -valid.

We showed that $\mathcal{I}'(\pi_v)$ is \mathcal{T} -valid for every $\pi_v \in \Pi_R(G, \xi)$, i.e. $\Pi_R(G, \xi)$ is SAT. \square

Proof (Sketch, Theorem 3).

Let us denote by $\mathbb{P}' = \mathbb{P} \cup \{\rho_{m+1}, \dots, \rho_q\}$ the set of predicates after refinement. In addition we denote by $\hat{B} := B \cup \{b_{m+1}, \dots, b_q\}$ the set of Boolean variables for \mathbb{P}' .

Next, assume by contradiction that there exists a hyper resolution proof of unsatisfiability G' for $\Pi_{\mathbb{P}'}$ such that G has the same structure as G (i.e. $V = V'$ and $E = E'$) and for every $v \in V$ it holds that $L_S(v)$ and $L'_S(v)$ agree on variables in $X \cup X' \cup B \cup B'$.

Let v be a node in G and let $\sigma'_v = L'_S(v)$ be the substitution mapped to v in G' . Recall that σ'_v agrees with $L_S(v)$ on the variables in $X \cup X' \cup B \cup B'$. We now prove that G' is also a proof of unsatisfiability for Π_R . First, we prove by induction on the structure of G' that $\sigma'_v \models \mathcal{I}(I_v)$.

- Base: Let $v \in V'_I$ be an internal node such that $in(v) = \{in_T(v)\}$. In this case, according to Lemma 2: $L'_F(in_T(v))$ is of the form: $\eta(X) \wedge \bigwedge_{j=1}^q (b_j \leftrightarrow \rho_j(X)) \rightarrow \hat{H}(\hat{B})$. From Definition 1 we know that $\sigma'_v \models \eta(X) \wedge \bigwedge_{j=1}^q (b_j \leftrightarrow \rho_j(X))$. Moreover, since \mathcal{I} is a solution to Π_R we know that $\eta(X) \wedge \xi(X, B, \sigma) \rightarrow \mathcal{I}(I_v)$, where $\sigma = L_S(v)$ is valid. Recall that σ'_v agrees with σ on $X \cup X' \cup B \cup B'$. As a result, it follows that $\sigma'_v \models \xi(X, B, L_S(v))$. Hence, we get that $\sigma'_v \models \mathcal{I}(I_v)$.
- Step: Let $v \in V_I$ where $|in(v)| > 1$. By the induction hypothesis we get that $\forall u \in in(v) \setminus \{in_T(v)\} : \sigma'_u \models \mathcal{I}(I_u)$. Moreover, in this case, $L'_F(in_T(v))$ is of the form:

$$\bigwedge_{i=1}^n \hat{P}_i(B') \wedge \bigwedge_{j=1}^q ((b'_j \leftrightarrow \rho_j(X')) \wedge (b_j \leftrightarrow \rho_j(X))) \wedge \delta(X, X') \rightarrow \hat{H}(B)$$

Again, following Definition 1 we have that $\sigma'_v \models \bigwedge_{j=1}^q ((b'_j \leftrightarrow \rho_j(X')) \wedge (b_j \leftrightarrow \rho_j(X))) \wedge \delta(X, X')$. Next, given \mathcal{I} is a solution to Π_R we have that:

$$\bigwedge_{u \in in(v) \setminus \{in_T(v)\}} \mathcal{I}(I_u)(X') \wedge \xi(X', B', \sigma) \wedge \xi(X, B, \sigma) \wedge \delta(X, X') \rightarrow \mathcal{I}(I_v)(X)$$

where $\sigma = L_S(v)$. Following similar arguments to those of the base case it follows that $\sigma'_v \models \xi(X', B', \sigma) \wedge \xi(X, B, \sigma) \wedge \delta(X, X')$ and as a result, $\sigma'_v \models \mathcal{I}(I_v)$.

Lastly, using this claim, we get that for the root node r , where $L'_F(in_T(r))$ is of the form:

$$\bigwedge_{i=1}^n \hat{P}_i(B) \wedge \bigwedge_{j=1}^q (b_j \leftrightarrow \rho_j(X)) \wedge \eta(X) \rightarrow \perp$$

It holds that $\forall u \in in(r) \setminus \{in_T(r)\} : \sigma'_u \models \mathcal{I}(I_u)$. In addition, since σ'_u agrees with $\sigma_u = L_S(u)$ on $X \cup X' \cup B \cup B'$, we have that $\sigma'_u \models \bigwedge_{j=1}^q (b_j \leftrightarrow$

$\rho_j(X) \wedge \eta(X)$. This is a contradiction to the fact that the following formula is valid:

$$\bigwedge_{u \in \text{in}(r) \setminus \{\text{in}_T(r)\}} \mathcal{I}(I_u)(X) \wedge \xi(X, B, L_S(v)) \wedge \eta(X) \rightarrow \perp$$

□